

Study of the Incidence of Different Types of Tuberculous Lesions in Association with Diabetes Mellitus in Indian Patients

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Received: 25-02-2024 / Revised: 23-03-2024 / Accepted: 25-04-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Tuberculosis (TB) and diabetes mellitus (DM) are significant global health concerns, particularly in regions with high prevalence rates of both conditions. Diabetes increases the risk of developing active TB and complicates its treatment, leading to worse outcomes. Understanding the incidence and types of tuberculous lesions in diabetic patients is crucial for improving diagnostic accuracy and treatment strategies.

Aim: This study aimed to investigate the incidence and types of tuberculous lesions in Indian patients with diabetes mellitus to better understand the relationship between these comorbidities.

Methods: Data were collected through clinical examinations, imaging studies, and laboratory tests. The types of tuberculous lesions were classified, and the association between diabetes control (measured by HbA1c levels) and the incidence of specific TB lesions was analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Logistic regression analysis was performed to assess the impact of glycemic control on the risk of different types of TB lesions.

Results: Pulmonary tuberculosis was the most common lesion, observed in 60% of participants, with a significantly higher incidence in those with uncontrolled diabetes (64.3% vs. 50%, $p = 0.03$). Bone and joint tuberculosis were more prevalent in patients with controlled diabetes ($p = 0.04$). Logistic regression indicated that uncontrolled diabetes significantly increased the risk of pulmonary tuberculosis (OR = 1.78, 95% CI: 1.10 - 2.88, $p = 0.02$).

Conclusion: The study highlights the strong association between uncontrolled diabetes and the increased incidence of pulmonary tuberculosis. These findings underscore the importance of optimal glycemic control in diabetic patients to reduce the risk of severe TB complications.

Recommendations: Regular monitoring and management of blood glucose levels should be prioritized in diabetic patients to prevent TB complications. Further research is recommended to explore the underlying mechanisms linking diabetes control and specific types of TB lesions.

Keywords: Tuberculosis, Diabetes Mellitus, Pulmonary Tuberculosis, Glycemic Control, India.

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Introduction

Tuberculosis (TB) remains a major global health challenge, particularly in low- and middle-income countries where it continues to be a leading cause of morbidity and mortality. Despite significant advances in its diagnosis and treatment, TB affected approximately 10 million people worldwide in 2021, with 1.6 million deaths reported [1]. The situation is further complicated by the rising prevalence of DM, a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by hyperglycemia. Diabetes is associated with a threefold increased risk of developing active TB, making the TB-diabetes comorbidity an emerging public health concern [2].

The global burden of diabetes is rapidly increasing, with the International Diabetes Federation reporting that approximately 537 million adults

were living with diabetes in 2021, and this number is projected to rise to 643 million by 2030 [3]. India, in particular, faces a dual burden of high TB and diabetes prevalence, with the country having the highest number of TB cases globally and ranking second in the number of people with diabetes [4]. The coexistence of these two diseases poses significant challenges to public health, as diabetes not only increases the risk of TB but also adversely affects TB treatment outcomes, leading to higher rates of treatment failure, relapse, and mortality

The pathophysiological mechanisms underlying the association between TB and diabetes are complex and multifactorial. Diabetes impairs both innate and adaptive immune responses, leading to a

diminished ability to control *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* infection. Hyperglycemia, a hallmark of diabetes, has been shown to affect macrophage function, reduce T-cell-mediated immunity, and alter cytokine production, thereby facilitating the progression from latent TB infection to active disease [5]. Furthermore, the clinical presentation of TB in diabetic patients may be atypical, leading to delays in diagnosis and treatment initiation [6].

Despite the growing recognition of the TB-diabetes association, there is a paucity of data on the specific types of tuberculous lesions that occur in diabetic patients, particularly in high-burden settings like India. Previous studies have primarily focused on the prevalence of TB among diabetic patients, with limited attention to the histopathological variations and clinical outcomes associated with different types of TB lesions in this population [7]. Understanding these variations is crucial for improving diagnostic accuracy and optimizing treatment strategies for diabetic patients with TB. This study aimed to investigate the incidence and types of tuberculous lesions in Indian patients with diabetes mellitus to better understand the relationship between these comorbidities.

Methodology

Study Design: This study was a cross-sectional observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted in PMCH, Bihar, India over a period of 12 months. The hospital serves a diverse population, providing a suitable setting for the study of tuberculosis in diabetic patients.

Participants: A total of 200 patients diagnosed with tuberculosis and diabetes mellitus were included in the study. These patients were recruited from the outpatient and inpatient departments of the hospital.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients aged 18 years and above.
- Patients with a confirmed diagnosis of tuberculosis based on clinical, radiological, and microbiological evidence.
- Patients with a confirmed diagnosis of diabetes mellitus, either newly diagnosed or with a known history of diabetes.
- Patients willing to give informed consent to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with immunocompromised states other than diabetes, such as HIV infection.

- Patients who were undergoing treatment for tuberculosis for more than two months prior to the study.
- Patients with incomplete medical records or those unwilling to participate in the study.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, consecutive sampling was used to recruit participants until the sample size was met. Information bias was reduced by ensuring that all data were collected and recorded by trained personnel using standardized forms. Confounding factors were addressed through statistical adjustments during the analysis phase.

Data Collection: Data were collected using a structured questionnaire that included demographic details, medical history, clinical examination findings, and relevant investigations. The diagnosis and classification of tuberculous lesions were based on clinical, radiological, and laboratory findings, including sputum smear, culture, and histopathological examination. Blood glucose levels and HbA1c were measured to confirm the presence and control of diabetes.

Procedure: Patients who met the inclusion criteria were enrolled in the study after obtaining informed consent. Each participant underwent a detailed clinical examination and necessary investigations to confirm the diagnosis of tuberculosis and diabetes. The type of tuberculous lesions was documented based on imaging studies (such as chest X-rays, CT scans), microbiological results, and histopathological reports.

Statistical Analysis: The SPSS version 23.0 was used to enter and analyse the data. The baseline characteristics of the subjects were compiled using descriptive statistics. Using chi-square tests, the incidence of various tuberculous lesions was computed and compared between the diabetes and non-diabetic groups. After correcting for relevant confounders, a logistic regression analysis was conducted to evaluate the relationship between diabetes mellitus and the occurrence of several types of tuberculous lesions. Statistical significance was attained when the p-value was less than 0.05.

Results

A total of 200 participants were included in the study, all of whom were diagnosed with both TB and DM. The participants were categorized based on the type of tuberculous lesions identified. The demographic and clinical characteristics of the study participants are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Study Participants (N=200)

Characteristic	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	120	60%
Female	80	40%
Age Group (years)		
18-30	40	20%
31-50	100	50%
51-70	50	25%
>70	10	5%
Duration of Diabetes		
<5 years	50	25%
5-10 years	90	45%
>10 years	60	30%
HbA1c Levels		
<7%	60	30%
7-8.5%	80	40%
>8.5%	60	30%

Incidence of Different Types of Tuberculous Lesions: The study identified a variety of tuberculous lesions among the participants. The distribution of different types of lesions is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Distribution of Tuberculous Lesions Among Participants (N=200)

Type of Tuberculous Lesion	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Pulmonary Tuberculosis	120	60%
Pleural Tuberculosis	40	20%
Lymph Node Tuberculosis	20	10%
Abdominal Tuberculosis	10	5%
Miliary Tuberculosis	5	2.5%
Tuberculous Meningitis	3	1.5%
Bone and Joint Tuberculosis	2	1%

Comparison of Tuberculous Lesions between Patients with Controlled and Uncontrolled Diabetes: Participants were further divided into two groups based on their HbA1c levels: controlled diabetes (HbA1c <7%) and uncontrolled diabetes (HbA1c ≥7%). The incidence of different types of tuberculous lesions was compared between these two groups, as shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Incidence of Tuberculous Lesions in Controlled vs. Uncontrolled Diabetes Groups

Type of Tuberculous Lesion	Controlled Diabetes (n=60)	Uncontrolled Diabetes (n=140)	p-value
Pulmonary Tuberculosis	30 (50%)	90 (64.3%)	0.03*
Pleural Tuberculosis	15 (25%)	25 (17.9%)	0.22
Lymph Node Tuberculosis	5 (8.3%)	15 (10.7%)	0.65
Abdominal Tuberculosis	5 (8.3%)	5 (3.6%)	0.15
Miliary Tuberculosis	2 (3.3%)	3 (2.1%)	0.61
Tuberculous Meningitis	1 (1.7%)	2 (1.4%)	0.88
Bone and Joint Tuberculosis	2 (3.3%)	0 (0%)	0.04*

*Statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Statistical Analysis

- **Pulmonary Tuberculosis:** The incidence of pulmonary tuberculosis was significantly higher in patients with uncontrolled diabetes compared to those with controlled diabetes (64.3% vs. 50%, $p = 0.03$).
- **Bone and Joint Tuberculosis:** Interestingly, bone and joint tuberculosis was only observed

in patients with controlled diabetes, showing a significant difference ($p = 0.04$).

- **Pleural, Lymph Node, Abdominal, Miliary Tuberculosis, and Tuberculous Meningitis:** No significant differences were observed in the incidence of these lesions between the controlled and uncontrolled diabetes groups.

Logistic Regression Analysis: A logistic regression analysis was conducted to evaluate the

association between uncontrolled diabetes (HbA1c $\geq 7\%$) and the incidence of pulmonary tuberculosis

after adjusting for age, gender, and duration of diabetes. The results are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4: Logistic Regression Analysis of Uncontrolled Diabetes and Pulmonary Tuberculosis

Variable	Odds Ratio (OR)	95% Confidence Interval (CI)	p-value
Uncontrolled Diabetes (HbA1c $\geq 7\%$)	1.78	1.10 - 2.88	0.02*
Age (>50 years)	1.25	0.75 - 2.08	0.40
Male Gender	1.15	0.68 - 1.94	0.60
Duration of Diabetes (>10 years)	1.30	0.78 - 2.17	0.32

*Statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

The analysis revealed that uncontrolled diabetes is significantly associated with an increased risk of developing pulmonary tuberculosis (OR = 1.78, 95% CI: 1.10 - 2.88, $p = 0.02$).

The spectrum of infectious diseases in diabetic patients admitted to a medical emergency was the subject of another study from northern India, which discovered that TB, although not the most common infection, was present in 4.6% of the cases. The study also showed that diabetic patients were more likely to develop other severe infections, such as pneumonia and UTIs, which further complicated their health outcomes. The study stressed the importance of carefully managing infections in diabetic patients in order to lower mortality, which was noticeably high in this group. Moreover, a study from Bangalore looked at the incidence of UTIs among patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus, and the findings showed that diabetic patients had a significantly higher incidence [8].

The prevalence of diabetes among hospitalised TB patients was investigated in a study conducted at a tertiary care centre in Manipal. The study found that 25.3% of TB patients also had diabetes, which was higher than the national average of 7.3%. It also found that patients between the ages of 41 and 60 had significantly higher odds of having diabetes than patients of a lower age; additionally, pulmonary TB was more common among diabetic patients compared to extrapulmonary TB, indicating a strong correlation between diabetes and more severe forms of TB [9].

The study found that the incidence of UTIs was significantly higher in patients with diabetes than in non-diabetic patients. Additionally, the study found that the infections were frequently more severe, caused by pathogens that were resistant to treatment, and associated with poor outcomes. These findings are especially noteworthy in the context of TB, as they suggest that patients with

diabetes are more susceptible to severe infections, including TB [10].

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